

VERB SEMANTICS IN TRANSLATION OF OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS FROM
HINDI (EXAMPLE OF THE OFFICIAL LANGUAGE ACT OF INDIA (1963))

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Annotation: *This article deals with the expression of verbs in official texts in Hindi and the issues of their translation. Issues such as the synonymy of verbs, their correct translation, and attention to style are reflected.*

Keywords: प्रवृत्त होता, नियत करना, गठित करना, निर्वाचित होना, असंगत, *official texts, documents, translation, hindi, verbs.*

Formal style is a style that requires special translation skills, in which the necessary knowledge and high vocabulary are important. Formal work style, legal, diplomatic documents - all require a clear translation, unlike literary translation, it is not always possible to use a word close to it instead of one word, or to enrich the translation with words. . The official style has a well-established language, which is difficult to translate without knowing the language.

Formal style is a way of speaking. This style is characterized by neutrality. There is no room for ambiguity in this style.

Hindi is a language formed on the basis of not one, but several languages, so the vocabulary of this language is also considerable. In this context, it can be said that a single word can be used in different senses in different styles, which requires more attention in the translation process. In particular, formal-style materials also contain stereotypes, and using them in other senses can lead to rough translation.

In particular, words belonging to the verb category have different meanings in each language. For example, in Hindi, the verb प्रवृत्त होता (pravṛtta hōtā) has many meanings, including inclination, inclination, increase, and capture. However, in official documents, the word often means "to remain in force", "to act":

“नियत दिन’ से, धारा ३ के सम्बन्ध में, जनवरी, 1965 का 26वां दिन अभिप्रेत है और इस अधिनियम के किसी अन्य उपबन्ध के सम्बन्ध में वह दिन अभिप्रेत है जिस दिन को वह उपबन्ध प्रवृत्त होता है;”¹

("Fixed date" means the date on which, in accordance with paragraph 3, January 26, 1965, in respect of any other provision of this Law, this provision shall enter into force;)

Or take the verb नियत करना (niyata karanā). This verb is often used in the verb to mean "destined", "destined", "seriously intended". However, in the formal style, this form of the verb basically means "determined", "determine", "appoint".

धारा ३, जनवरी, 1965 के 26 वें दिन को प्रवृत्त होगी और इस अधिनियम के शेष उपबन्ध उस तारीख को प्रवृत्त होंगे जिसे केन्द्रीय सरकार, शासकीय राजपत्र में अधिसूचना द्वारा नियत करे और इस अधिनियम के विभिन्न उपबन्धों के लिए विभिन्न तारीखें नियत की जा सकेंगी²

(Paragraph 3 shall enter into force on January 26, 1965, and the remaining provisions of this Act shall enter into force on the date on which the Central Government may be appointed by notice in the official Gazette and on different dates.)

As you can see, there are several verbs नियत करना (niyata karanā) in a single sentence, and they all mean "to be appointed."

Here is another example:

जिस तारीख को धारा ३ प्रवृत्त होती है उससे दस वर्ष की समाप्ति के पश्चात, राजभाषा के सम्बन्ध में एक समिति, इस विषय का संकल्प संसद के किसी भी सदन में राष्ट्रपति की पूर्व मंजूरी से प्रस्तावित और दोनों सदनों द्वारा पारित किए जाने पर, गठित की जाएगी.

(Ten years after the entry into force of Section 3, the State Language Committee shall be established with the previous permission of the President in accordance with the decision on the issue proposed in any chamber of parliament.)

The above text ends with the compound verb गठित की जाएगी (gaṭhita kī jāēēī). In the Uzbek translation, this verb is expressed by the verb "is formed". The word can also be expressed as "organized." If a word needs to be translated from Uzbek into Hindi, a translator who is not familiar with the terms in the field can translate बनाना, बना देना, निर्मित करना (banānā, banā dēnā, nirmita karanā), and in some places संस्थापित करना (sansthāpita karanā). However, it is incorrect to use these words in all parts of official documents. गठित करना (Gaṭhita karanā) officially means “to organize, to form” and means

¹ राजभाषा अधिनियम, 1963

² राजभाषा अधिनियम, 1963

to form an organization or collective structure in a legally step-by-step way, and in this way is radically different from its other synonyms.

इस समिति में तीस सदस्य होंगे जिनमें से बीस लोक सभा के सदस्य होंगे तथा दस राज्य सभा के सदस्य होंगे, जो क्रमशः लोक सभा के सदस्यों तथा राज्य सभा के सदस्यों द्वारा आनुपातिक प्रतिनिधित्व पद्धति के अनुसार एकल संक्रमणीय मत द्वारा निर्वाचित होंगे।³

(The committee consists of thirty members, of whom twenty are members of Lok Sabha and ten are members of Rajya Sabha, respectively, members of Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha are elected by proportional representation by a single ballot, respectively.)

The verb *nirvācīta hōnā* in the example above means, "to be chosen." The verb also means "return", "return", and «return of something". If, in the process of translation, the word is translated literally without knowing the meaning within the text, the content of the translation will change, making it difficult for the translator. Therefore, it is advisable to get acquainted with the official style and related terms before connecting the translation of official documents.

We would like to draw your attention to the associations of Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha given in the above translation: Rajya Sabha is the Upper House of Parliament (Oliy Majlis) and Lok Sabha is the Lower House (Legislative Chamber). It is worthwhile to explain such terms separately.

In a formal style, words used in a different sense will be molded in a completely different sense. For this reason, it is important not to confuse the meaning of the translation during the translation process.

राष्ट्रपति उपधारा (३) में निर्दिष्ट प्रतिवेदन पर और उस पर राज्य सरकारों ने यदि कोई मत अभिव्यक्त किए हों तो उन पर विचार करने के पश्चात् उस समस्त प्रतिवेदन के या उसके किसी भाग के अनुसार निदेश निकाल सकेगा : परन्तु इस प्रकार निकाले गए निदेश धारा ३ के उपबन्धों से असंगत नहीं होंगे ।

(The President, after reviewing the report referred to in paragraph 3 and the views expressed by the state governments, if any, may issue instructions in whole or in part in this report: unless it contradicts the rules of lim.)

The word **असंगत** (*asaṅgata*) is a plural word meaning "inappropriate", "irrelevant", "insignificant". The above sentence is translated as "contradictory" depending on the content of the text. Therefore, it is appropriate to translate the word as "conformity".

³ राजभाषा अधिनियम, 1963

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